

Management

ATTITUDE TOWARDS HANDLING OF EMPTY PACKAGED DRINKING WATER BOTTLE

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ABSTRACT

Water is one of most essential product for our life. Without water any living beings cannot live for a longer period of time. Water is one of the important top five sources for all. Role of water cannot be measured. Such the vital role is done by water in the body. It gives strength, clear all unnecessary contains from our body, refresh our flesh, and maintain correct temperature and so on. It is very much important that drinking a good water. These days, water is highly polluted due to the industrial growth. Therefore, water is sold in the packet. As it is little difficult to bring water wherever we go, people prefer to buy this packaged water. After drinking the water, people simply throw the packet in the dustbin. It creates the environment pollution problem. Now, green management has very important to protect the world from pollution. It urges the scholar to study about the importance of the packet water and how can be protected our environment from these waste. It also deals with giving suggestion to use packet water without pollute the environment.

Keywords:

Water, Packet, Pollution, Environment, Green Management & Unhealthy.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Today, millions of people are drinking unhealthy water in the world. Each year 5 million people worldwide die due to the diseases caused by unhealthy drinking water. Unhealthy water creates a great risk, especially for children because of their undeveloped immune system (G8 Action Plan Decisions, 2003)¹. In developed countries, it is observed that water is not only a basic consumption food, but also a lifestyle product.

The consumption of bottled mineral water is significantly increasing worldwide and has become an important factor both for economic and health issues (King, 2008)².

Consumption of bottled water is increasing by ten percent every year worldwide, with the fastest growth is seen in the developing countries of Asia and South America. The United States (U.S.) is the largest consumer market for bottled water in the world (Gleick 2004 – 2005)³.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

In the modern scientific world most of the consumers, both poor and rich, are using packaged drinking water frequently or occasionally.

Plastic bottles are a waste problem adding to landfill overload when not recycled and they cause number of environmental and social concerns (Glennon 2002).

Hence, the researcher has made an attempt to find out the attitude of consumers towards handling of empty packaged drinking water bottle.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of the study,

- 1) To know the attitude of the consumers towards handling of empty packaged drinking water bottle.
- 2) To analysis the awareness of consumers towards recycling of empty packaged drinking water bottle.

4. HYPOTHESES

- 1) Awareness of handling empty packaged drinking water bottle not based on the education of the consumers.
- 2) Handling of empty packaged drinking water bottle do not influenced by occupation of the respondents.

5. METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

- 1) Since the study has its own predetermined objectives and methodology, it is descriptive in nature and this part of research.
- 2) 2. Statistical tool SPSS (17.0) has been applied to classify and analyse the data collected in the survey undertaken. The collected data were processed with the help of appropriate statistical tools.

Chi-Square Analysis: The Chi-Square analysis has been used to analyse the influence of education and awareness of respondents with the handling of empty packaged drinking water bottle.

Figure 1: Handling of Empty Bottle after Use

Fig .1 shows the handling of empty bottles after use. Majority of the respondents (39.0%) recycle the empty bottle after use; it is followed by reuse (36.2%), throw away (15.7%) and crush (9.1%). Majority of the respondents sell to recycle the empty bottle after use.

Table 1: Age of the Respondents and Handling of Empty Bottles after Use

Age		Empty bottle after use				Total
		Throw away	Reuse	Crush	Sell to Recycle	
Below 18	No of Respondents	2	28	3	35	68
	Percentage	2.1%	12.7%	5.5%	14.8%	11.2%
18-25	No of Respondents	40	74	15	79	208
	Percentage	42.1%	33.6%	27.3%	33.3%	34.3%
26-33	No of Respondents	29	46	16	91	182
	Percentage	30.5%	20.9%	29.1%	38.4%	30.0%
34-40	No of Respondents	8	35	13	19	75
	Percentage	8.4%	15.9%	23.6%	8.0%	12.4%
Above 40 years	No of Respondents	16	37	8	13	74
	Percentage	16.8%	16.8%	14.5%	5.5%	12.2%
Total	No of Respondents	95	220	55	237	607
	Percentage	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 shows the age group of the respondents and the handling of empty bottles after use. Majority of the respondents (34.3%) who are in the age group of 18-25 years throw away the empty bottle (42.1%). It is followed by 33.6% of them who reuse and recycle the empty bottles. 30.0% of the respondents are in the age group of 26-30 years. In it, 38.4% recycle, followed by those who throw away (30.5%) the empty bottle after use. Further, 12.4% of the respondents are in the age group of 34-40 years. Among them, 23.6% crush the empty bottle, reuse (8.4%) and sell to recycle. Finally, 11.2% of the respondents are in the age group of below 18 years and among them recycle (14.8%), reuse (12.7%) and throw away (2.1%) the empty bottle after use. It is concluded that the majority of the respondents who are in the age groups of 18 – 25 yrs takes important role in throw away, reuse and crash the empty bottle. Though in the age group of 26 – 33 years sell to recycling the empty bottles.

Table 2: Association between Handling of Empty Bottle and Age of the Respondents

	Value	Df	P value
Pearson Chi-Square	53.276 ^a	12	.000*
Likelihood Ratio	58.121	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	11.153	1	.001
N of Valid Cases	607		

*Significant at 5% level

Table 2 shows that the Chi square value of 53.276 (df=12, N=607) P<0.05 is significant at 12 degrees of freedom, showing there is a significant difference between expected and observed frequencies. As such, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Hence, it is concluded that the respondents' age influences the handling of empty bottles after use.

Table 3: Ducation and Handling of Empty Bottles

Education		Users of empty bottle after use				Total
		Throw away	Reuse	Crush	Sell to Recycle	
Illiterate	No of Respondents	9	15	5	10	39
	Percentage	9.5%	6.8%	9.1%	4.2%	6.4%

School level	No of Respondents	31	92	15	128	266
	Percentage	32.6%	41.8%	27.3%	54.0%	43.8%
College level	No of Respondents	55	113	35	99	302
	Percentage	57.9%	51.4%	63.6%	41.8%	49.8%
Total	No of Respondents	95	220	55	237	607
	Percentage	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: primary Data

Table 3 shows the relationship between the education of the respondents and the handling of empty bottle after use. At the different levels of education, college level respondents (49.8%) use packaged drinking water more. In it, 57.9% of them throw away the empty bottles after use followed by reuse (51.4%) and crush (63.6%). In the school level educated respondents, (54.0%), recycle, reuse (41.8%) and throw away (32.6%) the empty bottles. Finally, among the 6.4% the illiterate respondents, 9.5% throw away reuse (6.8%) and sell to recycle (4.2%) the empty bottles. Majority of the educated respondents reuse the empty bottles.

Table 4: Association between Handling of Empty Bottle and Education of the Respondents

	Value	df	P value
Pearson Chi-Square	22.341 ^a	6	.001*
Likelihood Ratio	22.698	6	.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.298	1	.130
N of Valid Cases	607		

*Significant at 5% level

Table 4 shows the relationship between the education of the respondents and the handling of empty bottles after use. As per the rejection of null hypothesis ($P < 0.05$) the education of the respondents influences the handling of empty bottles after use. The handling of empty bottles is closely related with the education of the respondents.

Table 5: Occupation of the Respondents and Handling of Empty Bottle

Occupation		Users of empty bottle after use				Total
		Throw away	Reuse	Crush	Sell to Recycle	
Employed	No of Respondents	35	81	23	53	192
	Percentage	36.8%	36.8%	41.8%	22.4%	31.6%
Business	No of Respondents	15	40	9	95	159
	Percentage	15.8%	18.2%	16.4%	40.1%	26.2%
Housewife	No of Respondents	26	45	11	43	125
	Percentage	27.4%	20.5%	20.0%	18.1%	20.6%
Labourers	No of Respondents	8	26	2	5	41
	Percentage	8.4%	11.8%	3.6%	2.1%	6.8%
Students	No of Respondents	11	28	10	41	90
	Percentage	11.6%	12.7%	18.2%	17.3%	14.8%
Total	No of Respondents	95	220	55	237	607
	Percentage	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 shows the different occupations of the respondents and their handling of empty bottle. Majority of the respondents (31.6%) are employed. In it, 41.8% of them crush the empty bottle, 36.8% throw away and 36.8% reuse the empty bottle after use. 26.2% of the respondents are business people. Among them, 40.1% of them sell to recycle the empty bottle, 16.4% crush and 15.8% throw away the empty bottle. Further, 20.6% of the housewife respondents are house wives throw away are (27.4%). Here, it is followed by reuse (20.5%) and sell to recycle (18.1%). Finally, 14.8% of the respondents are students. Among them, 18.2% of them crush the empty bottle, 12.7% reuse and 11.6% throw away the empty bottle. Only 6.8% of the respondents are labourers. Among them, 11.8% reuse the empty bottle, 3.6% crush it and 2.1% sell to recycle the empty water bottle after use.

Table 6: Association of Occupation with Handling of Empty Bottle

	Value	df	P value
Pearson Chi-Square	62.379 ^a	12	.000*
Likelihood Ratio	63.223	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.390	1	.532
N of Valid Cases	607		

*Significant at 5% level

Table 6 shows the relationship between the occupation of the respondents and the handling of empty bottle. As per the rejection of null hypothesis ($P < 0.05$), occupation is associated with the handling of empty bottles after use. Hence, handling of empty bottle is influenced by the occupation of the respondents.

Table 7: Influence of Awareness in Handling of Empty Bottles

		N			F value	P value
T.V	Throw away	95	2.77	1.484	5.485	.001*
	Reuse	220	2.27	1.406		
	Crush	55	1.84	1.330		
	Sell to Recycle	237	2.31	1.394		
Internet	Throw away	95	2.48	1.359	2.004	.112*
	Reuse	220	2.19	1.285		
	Crush	55	1.96	1.374		
	Sell to Recycle	237	2.26	1.339		
Radio	Throw away	95	2.46	1.367	3.103	.026*
	Reuse	220	2.13	1.236		
	Crush	55	1.91	1.405		
	Sell to Recycle	237	2.34	1.313		
Press	Throw away	95	2.44	1.374	1.295	.275*
	Reuse	220	2.26	1.300		
	Crush	55	2.04	1.453		
	Sell to Recycle	237	2.37	1.370		
Pamphlets	Throw away	95	2.48	1.413	3.185	.023*
	Reuse	220	2.42	1.439		
	Crush	55	1.87	1.248		

	Sell to Recycle	237	2.50	1.346		
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*Significant at 5% level

Table 7 shows that F-test values are 2.004 and 1.773. $P < 0.05$ is not significant, showing there is no significant relationship with internet, press and handling of empty bottle. Hence, internet and press are not related to the handling of empty bottles. As per the acceptance of the null hypothesis there is a significant difference between the variables T.V, radio, pamphlets and handling of empty bottles. It is concluded that the sources of information from T.V. and radio are useful for proper handling of empty bottles.

6. FINDINGS

- 1) Reusing empty bottles plays an important role in protecting the environment. Majority of the respondents prefer to reuse the empty bottles for other purposes of keeping oil, ordinary water and chemicals. Age, education and occupation influence the reusing of empty water bottles.
- 2) 40% of the respondents sell to the recycle the empty bottle. 9% of the respondents crush the empty bottle. 15% of the respondents throw away the empty bottle. 36% of the respondents reuse the empty packaged drinking water bottle.

7. SUGGESTIONS

- 1) Media like Television, radio and press should give proper information about the handling of empty packaged drinking water bottle.
- 2) The consumers should be educated on the use of empty packaged drinking water bottle.
- 3) Reusing empty packaged drinking water bottles plays dominant role in protecting the green environment. Majority of the respondents reuse the empty bottles for keeping oil, acid, phenol, and to carry drinking water. However, they never recycle the product. Both, central and state government should encourage and make arrangements to recycle the empty bottles for a healthy environment.

8. CONCLUSION

In modern days, packaged drinking water plays an important role in society due to scarcity of clean drinking water. Most of the respondents do not give importance to green environment. After using the packaged drinking water they throw away the bottles immediately. This creates lot of pollution in the society. The NGOs and government organizations should give importance to green environment by making appropriate arrangements for the reuse and recycling of these discarded containers and bottles.

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